

THERMAL BEHAVIOR OF TAPES IN AUTOMATED TAPE PLACEMENT (ATP) PROCESS-MICRO ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

A numerical model is presented to analyze the thermal behavior of the tapes at microscale during automated tape placement (ATP) process. A 3D geometrical model is developed considering the real microstructure. Ray tracing is used for the detection of the fibers impacted by the infrared laser. A heat source distribution is presented to show the difference between multiple tape microstructures. Finite element is used to solve this transient heat transfer problem of laser heating the tape for 25 milliseconds (ms) and then followed by subsequent cooling for next 25 ms. The temperature variation along the depth of the tape is presented and the depth at which the maximum temperature is present that differs depending on the microstructure. Moreover, the surface temperature variation along the time period of 50 ms are compared with the experimental results performed by an in-house instrumented bench.

1 INTRODUCTION

The huge demand for composite materials in multiple industrial sectors such as automobile, aeronautics, construction and many more, led to the necessity of advanced manufacturing techniques. Automated tape placement is one of these techniques that is based on the additive process of tapes layer by layer to give a high-end final product for industrial use. Despite the huge benefits of ATP in terms of labor-saving, accurate fiber placement, and quality improvements, the thermoset composite makes this process energy inefficient, expensive and time-consuming [1]. Therefore, the improvements in thermoplastic composite making it mechanically efficient and with low cycle time, advance the possibility to replace the thermoset counterparts[2]. Currently, thermoplastic are being used in various parts in an aero plane such as hoses[3], welded ribs, stamp formed clips[4] and many more. Yet its acceptance to replace the thermoset composite in large sized components is rather slow[1][4]. This can be possible by better understanding each phenomenon involved during the manufacturing of thermoplastic composite by the ATP process.

A typical ATP process involves the use of a motorized placement head to place the composite prepreg tapes layer by layer to build up a final laminate (Figure 1). The bonding of the surfaces involves intimate contact during heating by an infrared laser and subsequently pressing by a roller in the consolidation phase and later releasing the laminate to cool under atmospheric condition. The strength of the laminate is high when the bonding between the substrate and tape becomes strong. This is possible due to the decrease in the polymer viscosity during heating and increases the chances of better contact at the interface. Moreover, the intermolecular diffusion of the interface with intimate contact between the substrate and the tape due to autohesion increases the overall strength of the laminate[5]. Thus the phenomena of heating, pressing and autohesion are highly correlated. Furthermore, the temperature dependent factors such as void growth, melting crystallization, degradation makes the study of thermal transfer during the ATP process more important[6]. All these factors show that ATP is a widely temperature driven process.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of an ATP process [6]

There have been multiple research articles that are dedicated to the macroscale study of thermal behavior of the tapes. Generally, the temperature field is estimated by considering a surface heat source located on the top surface, thus disregarding the microscopic mechanisms of laser absorption at the fiber level. Nevertheless, at the microscale, there is a huge difficulty in predicting the real thermal behavior inside the tape during the heating of the top surface with a laser beam. Direct temperature measurement during the ATP process is often difficult due to the lack of confidence regarding the intrusiveness of the sensor between thin composite tapes ($\sim 500\mu\text{m}$). In the thesis of Le Louët [7], they developed a specific bench aiming to experimentally determine what prepreg tape undergo during a deposition in terms of temperatures. It was observed that with the classical model assuming tape as a homogenous medium, there is a bad prediction of the maximum temperature reached as well as of the temperature profile through the thickness of the tapes.

This paper focuses on overcoming the above limitation and that can be achieved by studying the thermal behavior at the microscale in the tape with a numerical approach. In this work, we consider the case where the laser heating is with a normal incidence with respect to the top surface of the tape. After image analysis of a tape micrograph recorded with an optical microscope to identify the positions of the fibers, the geometry is extruded in the fiber direction and a three dimensional (3D) mesh is generated. Similar to a ray tracing technique, the zones of the fibers impacted by the laser rays are first detected. Fibers are considered to be an absorbing medium and the matrix was assumed to be transparent [7]. The rear side of the tape accounts the roughness for the imperfect contact with the steel bench. The transient heat transfer equation is solved by FEM over the tape volume for a total time period of 50 ms out of which the tape was heated by a laser beam for 25 ms. The average surface temperature is measured through the time period of 50 ms and compared to the results obtained from the in-house experimental bench working towards thermal analysis on tapes [3]. The variation of temperature along the depth is studied numerically to better understand the maximum temperature of the tape reached after the heating phase. Moreover, the change in the heat source distribution for different microstructures is studied.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

An in-house experimental bench (Figure 2) was developed. A tape was held on metal support and is heated for a time of 25 ms by an infrared laser diode with a power P . Initially the objective was to measure the elevation of surface temperature generated by the absorption of a given amount of heat flux, depending on the angle of incidence θ of the laser. Under controlled conditions without parasitic reflections, surface temperature and absorbed flux are directly related to the radiative properties, topography, and microstructural arrangement of the carbon fibers under the heated face. The absorbed flux is then transmitted by conduction through the thickness of the tape, then at the interface with the metal frame[6].

The infrared camera could observe the top surface temperature of the tape but understanding the phenomena happening inside the tape is rather difficult, including the influence of the non-perfect contact between the tape and the steel. It is also important to understand that if the heat flux lines have

any constriction due to the imperfect contact at the rear side. This questions could be explained numerically by developing a model similar to the experimental approach and solving for the temperature distributions.

Figure 2: Experimental setup for microscopic measurement during ATP process

3 THERMAL MODELING OF TAPE IN ATP

The microscale thermal modeling of the tapes during the ATP process was done by solving the transient heat transfer equation (section 3.1). Two types of tapes from the Solvay group and Suprem are analyzed numerically. In section 3.2 the description of the geometry generated with the help of optical images of the tapes is described. The mesh from these geometries was made in a way that the surface of the fiber that has the direct impact of laser was detected and act as the heat source during the laser heating.

3.1 Numerical model

A schematic diagram shown in Figure 3 describes the basic idea of the model for tapes with direct laser heating and cooling by the steel bench on the rear side. The laser beam at $\theta = 0$ is assumed to be coming perpendicular to the surface with a flux of 1.8 MW m^{-2} (Q_{Laser}) [7]. The matrix acts as transparent to the laser heating and the fibers absorb 90% of the laser heating. In this preliminary model inter reflection was neglected. The air gap and non-smooth surface between the tape and steel act as the thermal contact resistance by giving added roughness. A transient heat transfer equation (1) is solved for T temperature by using finite element method in the sample by applying boundary conditions given by equation 2. ρC_p is the volumetric heat capacity, and k is the thermal conductivity.

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - \nabla k \nabla T = Q_{Laser} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{cases} \text{Boundary condition surface 'A', } -k \nabla T = 0 \\ \text{Boundary condition surface 'B', } T = 293K \\ \text{Initial condition, } T = 293K \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Figure 3: Schematic diagram for the numerical modeling

Thermal Properties	Fiber (AS4)	Matrix (PEEK) [7]	Air[8]	Steel [7]
$k(\text{W m}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1})$	6.1 Longitudinal [7] 1.19 Transversal	0.22	0.028	23.5
$C_p(\text{J kg}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1})$	1100 [9]	$683+3.75*T$ [K] ($T<416$ K) $593+4.49*T$ [K] ($T>416$ K)	1.006	480
$\rho(\text{kg m}^{-3})$	1790 [10]	1320	1.1	7700

TABLE 1: Material properties for the AS4 fibers, peek matrix

3.2 Image processing

The preliminary objective was to form a mesh for the finite element analysis that has maximum possible resemblance with the real microstructure. This was made possible by a Matlab code for treating the microscopic image of the tape to a binary image and then using the Hough algorithm [11] to detect the centre of the fiber. This data was passed on to GMSH, a finite element meshing tool, for the generation of a finite element mesh. The region of the fibers impacted by the laser are traced by simply taking the concept of ray tracing and detecting the elements that are coming in the first interaction of the laser beam with the fibers. These zones were detected with the help of a code developed in Matlab and the elements were changed to a different tag in order to later use this to act as the heat source for the tape. Figure 4 shows the basic schematic of the process for the generation of final mesh for the finite element analysis. Figure 5 shows the different microstructures of Solvay and Suprem tapes that were tested for the micro calculations of the ATP process.

Figure 4: Scheme for generation of mesh with laser impacted zones on fibers

Figure 5: Microstructures for numerical simulation (a) Solvay 1 (b) Solvay 2 (c) Solvay 3 (d) Suprem

4 HEAT SOURCE DISTRIBUTION

The heat source distributions along the height of the microstructures are determined by knowing the frequency or number of elements that are getting interacted by the laser at a particular height of the tape. This was done for each microstructure in order to better analyze the heat transfer inside the volume of the microstructure. With data fitting, a model (Beta function (MATLAB, 2013)) [12] was retrieved that can represent the heat source distribution. Figure 6(a) shows the heat source distribution in terms of frequency for Solvay 1 microstructure and fitting the data with a beta function. Figure 6(b) shows the heat source distribution for the different section of the same tape and it was observed that the heat source distribution could change significantly depending on the distribution of the fibers. This makes the homogeneity of the tape questionable. Figure 6(c) shows the distribution for a Suprem tape that has a peak close to the edge of the top surface. It was observed that the Suprem tape has a rather homogenous distribution of fibers throughout the microstructure making a similar heat source distribution for the different section of the tape.

Figure 6: Heat source distribution for different microstructures (a) Solvay 1 Frequency and fitting with beta function (b) Solvay microstructures (c) Suprem microstructures

5 RESULTS

In this section studies are shown on different microstructures after heating them with laser. This was achieved by implementing the finite element heat transfer model on different meshes that were generated in resemblance to the microstructure of tape.

5.1 Heat Flow during micro calculations

Figure 7 represents an initial representation of temperature at different time steps that could help in the visualization of what is happening at the micro scale. During initial heating by laser, the fibers that are facing the laser are getting heated and then after 25 ms the cooling begins as soon the heating is stopped. The fiber distribution in the microstructure is the controlling parameter as the fibers have nearly 10 times the thermal conductivity of the matrix. Figure 7(e) shows the streamlines after the interaction of the heat flow to the rear side of the tape that is in contact with the steel. The constriction of the streamlines at the rear side confirms the presence of the 2D heat flow as the streamlines are not straight. It is due to the preference of heating or cooling in particular pattern due to the alignment of fibers.

Figure 7: Temperature and Heat flow in Solvay 2 for (a) 0.5ms (b) 15ms (c) 25ms (d) 50ms (e) Flux lines at 25ms of heating (decreased opacity of the temperature distribution at (c)) (f) Temperature scale

5.2 Temperature variation along the height

As mentioned before, the difficulty of the ATP process is the measurement of the volume temperature distribution inside the tape due to its small size. This is numerically possible by the measurement of average temperature at a particular height y and then calculating the distribution of the temperature along the height. The average temperature is measured based on the grid concept at a particular height y . The cross-section at a particular height was divided into square grids and the mean of the temperature at all grid point calculates the average temperature at that height. Figure 8(a) shows the average temperature as a function of height (y) of the tape for different microstructures of Solvay tape. It can be seen that the maximum temperature is in little depths inside the surface. This is contrary to the assumption of homogenous behavior of the tape leading to the maximum temperature located at the surface as widely used in the literature for ATP process[5][13], Figure 8 (b) presents the temperature distribution for Suprem and it can be seen that although the maximum temperature is in less deep as compared to the Solvay. The depth of the maximum temperature varies depending on the microstructure distribution that also affects the heat source distribution.

Figure 8: Average temperature distribution along y at 25 ms (a) Solvay (b) Suprem

5.3 Temperature variation of the top surface with time

In this section, the temperature change observed by the infrared camera during experiments is compared with the surface temperature obtained by the numerical model. Figure 9(a) shows the temperature of the tape surface for a time period of 50 ms for different recorded microstructures of Solvay tape. For the heating time of 25 ms, there is a good agreement with the experimental results. However, the cooling rate is slow in case of numerical simulation in comparison with the experimental. This is because, during the heating time, the temperature is dominated by laser heating. But when laser heating is stopped, rest physical constraint such as volume fraction, contact zone, convection on the top and etc are also playing an important role. These factors should be considered in order to get a fully successful thermal analysis. These parameters need to be considered in more details in the future. Figure 9(b) shows the temperature change for the Suprem tape. It was observed that the surface temperature after 25ms of heating of the Suprem tapes is higher than the Solvay due to the fact that in Suprem the absorption of the heat is mostly at the fibers near to the top surface.

Figure 9: Comparison of average temperature of the top surface with experimental readings by the Infrared camera (a) Solvay (b) Suprem

6 CONCLUSION

A heat transfer model was presented for the microstructure of carbon/PEEK tapes in the ATP process. Different microstructures of Solvay tape along with Suprem tape were tested and its heat source distribution was presented. It was observed that the variation in fiber distribution in Solvay tape even in single tape can affect the overall volume heat source distribution of the microstructure. However, the heat source distribution for Suprem tapes was similar due to its homogenous fiber distribution. Similarly, for the Solvay tapes, the maximum temperature was in little depth inside the volume. Therefore the assumption of ATP process portraying surface heating fails as the maximum temperature observed was not on the surface. Thus the tape no more behaves as a homogenous medium with uniform temperature distribution with a maximum at the top surface.

An experimental and numerical result comparison of temperature observed by the Infrared camera was also done for two types of tapes. In the case of Solvay, the numerical model predicted that the temperature during heating is in good agreement, contrary to the cooling that was faster experimentally in comparison with the numerical results. The numerical results for Suprem tapes were also with a difference of a maximum 20°C with the experimental one. This could be due to the loss of volume fraction of the fibers during mesh generation. As loss of fibers could result in lowering the overall effective thermal conductivity of the tapes that results in slow cooling of the tapes. Moreover, the reflection is also neglected in the current tests. In the future, a more complete model will be tested that could take into account the reflection from the surface of the fiber. Additionally, a finer micrograph and mesh will be considered. This is expected to help in a better comparison of the cooling phenomena with the experimental results on the tapes during ATP.

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